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Journal of Communication Disorders

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/jcomdis

Assessing speech intelligibility of pathological speech in sentences and word lists: The contribution of phoneme-level measures

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Speech intelligibility
Phoneme
Speaker type classification
Severity level classification
Interrater reliability
Validity

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Speech intelligibility is an important indicator of the degree of speech impairment in pathological speech. Articulation, as a key feature of dysarthria, has been found to be a stronger contributor to intelligibility of dysarthric speech compared to voice quality, nasality, and prosody. In fact, therapy addressing articulation is often used by speech-language pathologists. Since phoneme-level measures are more directly related to articulation, they may contribute to better evaluating articulation imprecision in speakers with dysarthria and to monitoring the effectiveness of therapy.

Method: We collected two types of phoneme-level measures: a) Accuracy of Phonemes, the percentage of correctly transcribed phonemes, and b) Phonetic Distance, from orthographic transcriptions obtained from expert raters in two types of speech materials (i.e., meaningful sentences and word lists). We first examined the measures' interrater reliability using Generalizability Theory. Then we studied the validity of the measures by correlating them to three criterion variables. Following this, we explored their ability in distinguishing speakers in two classification tasks according to speakers' types (i.e., healthy vs dysarthric) and their severity levels of dysarthria, respectively.

Results: The results showed that both types of phoneme-level measures are highly reliable and valid in two different speech materials. They also showed acceptable results for both classification tasks in different speech materials, with word lists performing better than meaningful sentences. The differences between the two speech materials may be largely caused by differences in word structures and contextual cues in the materials.

Conclusion: The results indicate that both types of phoneme-level measures show largely similar reliability and validity in both speech materials. These measures perform better in word lists than in meaningful sentences, suggesting an advantage for using word lists in clinical practice and research. On the other hand, meaningful sentences can be used for classifying healthy and dysarthric speakers. Our results suggest that using different speech materials gives a better overview of the speakers' intelligibility at the segmental level and the implications of their articulation impairments.

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Received 20 May 2022; Received in revised form 28 December 2022; Accepted 20 January 2023

Available online 25 January 2023

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1. Introduction

Speech intelligibility is an important indicator of the degree of speech impairment in pathological speech and is often used by speech-language pathologists (SLPs) to diagnose individuals and evaluate the effectiveness of therapy (Van Riper & Emerick, 1984; Ishikawa et al., 2020). Individuals with dysarthria, a motor speech disorder caused by neurological injury (e.g., Parkinson's disease and stroke) experience difficulties in speech production that can lead to reduced speech intelligibility. To limit this loss in speech intelligibility and to even achieve some improvements, intensive speech therapy can be provided (Cannito et al., 2012; Levy et al., 2020; Nakayama et al., 2020; Yuan et al., 2020). To monitor therapy effectiveness, a clear definition of speech intelligibility is necessary. From many of the definitions presented in the literature, we adopted the one proposed by Hustad (2008, p.1): "Intelligibility refers to how well a speaker's acoustic signal can be accurately recovered by a listener". This definition automatically implies that speech intelligibility cannot be assessed without the participation of human listeners, either experts like speech-language pathologists or naïve listeners like college students. Common procedures of measuring intelligibility ask listeners to evaluate the intelligibility of different speech materials (e.g., a word list, a sentence or a passage) through different measurement methods (e.g., a visual analogue scale (VAS), an orthographic transcription, or a multiple-choice task).

Through these procedures, measures of intelligibility can be derived on different granularity levels, namely subword, word, sentence, and narrative. In this study, measures at the subword level refer to subword segments as basic units, namely phonemes, letters (graphemes), and syllables. Similarly, measures at the word level refer to the word as the basic unit, where words may occur either in isolation as in word lists or in sentences. Likewise, such definition can be generalized to sentence and narrative levels. It is important to note that some other studies used different names for the measures of the same unit in different speech materials. For example, a percentage of correctly transcribed words, considered as a word-level measure in this study, was named as "word intelligibility" or "single-word intelligibility" (Stipancic et al., 2016; Sussman & Tjaden, 2012; Yorkston & Beukelman, 1980, 1981) if the words were uttered in isolation, whereas it was named as "sentence intelligibility" if the words were presented and assessed for individual sentences (Abur et al., 2019; Stipancic et al., 2016; Sussman & Tjaden, 2012).

Measures of intelligibility perform differently in speech materials with varying lengths (Hustad, 2007; Yorkston & Beukelman, 1978; Miller, 2013; Xue et al., 2021a, b). For example, Hustad (2007) studied a word-level measure (i.e., percentage of correctly transcribed words) in three kinds of speech materials (i.e., word lists, sentences, and paragraphs). The author found higher intelligibility scores in paragraphs than in the other two types of materials. Xue et al. (2021b) studied the correlations of two measures (i.e., percentage of correctly transcribed words and ratings through VAS) between sentences and word lists. The correlations below 0.90 suggested that these two types of speech materials can result in different constructs of intelligibility being measured.

Further, the different performance in speech materials with varying lengths does not seem to be consistent across severity levels of dysarthria of speakers. First, when speech is mildly to moderately degraded or dysarthric, higher scores for word-level measures have been found on words in sentences than on words in isolation (Hustad, 2007; Yorkston & Beukelman, 1978, 1981). This may be due to the additional contextual cues provided by sentences. Second, when speech is more severely dysarthric, this difference between words in isolation and sentences seems to become less clear (Dongilli, 1994; Hustad, 2007; Miller, 2013; Yorkston & Beukelman, 1978, 1981). For instance, regarding intelligibility scores of profound dysarthric speech, some studies found higher scores on sentences than on words; some found equal scores (Barreto & Ortiz, 2008; Dongilli, 1994; Yorkston & Beukelman, 1978), while some others found lower scores (Yorkston & Beukelman, 1981). These inconsistencies between sentences and word lists may arise because speakers with more severe dysarthria have so many difficulties with pronunciation that listeners are no longer able to benefit from the contextual cues present in sentences.

Although measures can be derived at different granularity levels, intelligibility measures at the subword level may provide more detailed insights into misarticulation detections and their relationships with intelligibility, particularly at the segmental level. In fact, articulation is a key feature of dysarthria (Tjaden, 2007), and it has been found to be a stronger contributor to intelligibility compared to other speech characteristics (i.e., voice quality, nasality and prosody) (De Bodt et al., 2002). Also, therapy focusing on articulation has been preferred by many SLPs regardless of severity levels of dysarthria (Miller & Bloch, 2017). Therefore, studying subword-level measures can provide information on articulation impairment to help SLPs in diagnosing individuals and monitoring therapy.

For detecting misarticulation, measures at the phoneme level may be better than those at the grapheme and syllable levels. This is because languages may differ in their degree of orthographic depth (Katz & Frost, 1992), which is the consistency in relationships between graphemes and phonemes. English is often cited as an example of a deep orthography with inconsistent relationships, whereas Italian has more consistent relationships and is usually categorized as a shallow orthography. Dutch, the language under study, is somewhere in between, and in Dutch, a cluster of two graphemes may represent a single phoneme (Landerl & Reitsma, 2005). In addition, the same grapheme may represent different phonemes depending on the languages under study or the grapheme's position in a word. An example of the difference between languages is that vowel duration spelling ('aa' vs 'a') in Dutch is phonologically consistent in terms of a closed vs an open syllable but lexically inconsistent (e.g., 'paar'-'pa-ren' for singular - plural) whereas this is the opposite in German (e.g., 'Paar'-'Paa-re'). An example of the difference between different positions in a word is that in English, the letter A (lower case a) is usually pronounced /æ/ in closed syllables, like 'cat', and /eɪ/ in open syllables, like 'ta' in 'take'. Hence, for assessing articulation impairment and providing diagnostic information, phoneme-level measures may be more efficient than grapheme- and syllable-level measures. Therefore, the current study focuses on phoneme-level measures.

Until now, research on phoneme-level measures had several limitations. First of all, phoneme-level measures of intelligibility have been limited to word lists rather than sentences. In detail, these measures have been generally computed on word lists consisting of paired words with phoneme contrasts (Ansel & Kent, 1992; Kent et al., 1989; Kim et al., 2011; Levy et al., 2016). Considering that speech materials of different lengths can impact higher-level measures in different ways, it is necessary to study phoneme-level

measures in speech materials varying in length. In this way, phoneme-level measures may help explore the above-mentioned different performance of higher-level measures in sentences and word lists, as suggested in Xue et al. (2021b). In addition, existing studies of phoneme-level measures have considered only the target unit (Platt et al., 1980; Furia et al., 2001), such as target consonants and vowels in the Dutch Intelligibility Assessment (Middag, 2012), rather than all the units composing a word. This may lead to loss of articulation information and, thus, may impact the evaluation of the effectiveness of articulation therapy. Moreover, studying phoneme-level measures in sentences may help investigate speakers' articulation imprecision in this more natural condition, in which words occur within a meaningful context, compared to when they are uttered in isolation as in word lists. Therefore, it is worthy and necessary to consider differences in speech materials when investigating the impact of measures at the phoneme level.

In addition to the limitations of current research on phoneme-level measures, it is important to note that the reliability of intelligibility measures used can be affected by transcription instructions. Currently, two types of instructions have been studied for orthographic transcriptions. In one of them, denoted as Existing-Word Transcription (EWTrans; see Xue et al., 2021b), listeners are instructed to transcribe only existing, meaningful words that have the closest pronunciation to the words they heard. The other one instructs listeners to transcribe words consisting of phonemes that have the same pronunciations as what they heard, regardless of whether the transcribed words are meaningful or not. This type of transcription is denoted as Acceptable-Word Transcription (AWTrans) and was recently explored in Xue et al. (2021b).

Although EWTrans has been widely used (Abur et al., 2019; Barreto & Ortiz, 2008, 2016; Carvalho et al., 2020; Ganzeboom et al., 2016; Hodge & Gotzke, 2014; Hustad, 2006, 2007, 2008; Ishikawa et al., 2020; Liss et al., 2002; Middag, 2012; Miller, 2013; Stipancic et al., 2016; Tjaden & Liss, 1995a, 1995b, 2014, 2010; Sussman & Tjaden, 2012; Yorkston & Beukelman, 1978, 1981), it may generate intelligibility measures with lower reliability and poorer variability (i.e., scores were clustered rather than spread) than those obtained from AWTrans. For example, Xue et al. (2021a) found very low reliability (0.47) for a word-level measure of intelligibility, namely word accuracy (AcW), obtained through EWTrans, which was much lower than that for the measure of intelligibility obtained from VAS (0.93). Similarly, Xue et al. (2021b) examined AcW scores obtained from both EWTrans and AWTrans and found lower reliability of AcW in EWTrans (0.83) compared to that in AWTrans (0.89). Both reliability scores were lower than the reliability of VAS (0.93). In both studies mentioned above, the low reliability values of AcW obtained in EWTrans were caused by a ceiling effect. Many of the sentences received scores of 100, indicating perfect intelligibility, which led to poor variability of AcW scores in EWTrans. A possible explanation of the presence of perfect intelligibility in EWTrans is that raters, following the instructions, may transcribe the same meaningful words even if they perceived distortions, substitutions, deletions or insertions of a phoneme in a word. In contrast, AWTrans provides raters with more flexibility by allowing them to use pseudo words in transcriptions. The rich variability in AWTrans would be useful for providing diagnostic information since it may reflect smaller but relevant differences between the speakers. Therefore, to examine phoneme-level measures of intelligibility derived from transcriptions, AWTrans is preferred over EWTrans.

To fill the knowledge gaps presented above, this study, as a follow up to Xue et al. (2021b), aims to examine how phoneme-level intelligibility measures can complement higher-level intelligibility measures. Specifically, we explored what insights the phoneme-level intelligibility measures can provide in relation to two types of speech materials and two classification tasks. For the two types of speech materials, we considered meaningful sentences from a narrative and word lists consisting of words and pseudo words with a Consonant-Vowel-Consonant (CVC) structure. For the two classification tasks, we considered a two-way classification of speaker types (healthy vs dysarthric speakers) and a four-way classification of severity levels of dysarthria (SevL; healthy, mild, moderate, and severe) by splitting dysarthric speakers into three fine-grained levels. Two types of phoneme-level intelligibility measures extracted from AWTrans were studied: Accuracy of Phonemes (AcP), which is the percentage of correctly transcribed phonemes, and Phonetic Distance (PhonD), which is the degree of difference between transcribed phonemes and the target reference phonemes. We address three research questions:

- 1 RQ1: To what extent are phoneme-level intelligibility measures reliable across different types of speech materials?
- 2 RQ2: To what extent are phoneme-level intelligibility measures valid across different types of speech materials?
- 3 RQ3: To what extent are phoneme-level intelligibility measures able to classify speakers in speaker type and severity levels of dysarthria across different types of speech materials?

2. Methods

This study evaluates two types of phoneme-level measures of intelligibility (i.e., AcP and PhonD) in different speech materials regarding their reliability, validity, and performance in two classification tasks. The tasks included a two-way classification of speaker types and a four-way classification of severity levels of dysarthria. Both types of phoneme-level measures were derived from orthographic transcriptions in AWTrans form collected through two listening experiments described in Xue et al. (2021b). Each of the two listening experiments targeted only one type of speech material, namely the Sentence Experiment for the meaningful sentences and the Word Experiment for word lists consisting of CVC words. All the speech materials, speakers, and their recordings to be assessed in these two experiments were selected from the Corpus of Pathological and Normal Speech (COPAS) database¹ (Middag, 2012), which consists of a large number of recordings of various reading materials, such as isolated words, isolated sentences, short passages, and spontaneous speech, by speakers of Belgian-Dutch with and without speech disorders. Both listening experiments were conducted within the

¹ More information and the manual of COPAS can be found on <https://taalmaterialen.ivdnt.org/download/tstc-corpus-pathologische-en-normale-spraak-copas/>.

research project Developing valid measurement procedure of pathological speech intelligibility (application 2019–3197) that has been approved by the Ethics Assessment Committee Humanities of the Faculty of Arts and the Faculty of Philosophy, Theology and Religious Studies at the Radboud University with reference number Let/MvB19U.514400. (Xue et al., 2021b).

2.1. Speech material

Two types of speech materials were evaluated in two separate listening experiments, as mentioned above. The Sentence Experiment covered four meaningful sentences that were selected from the Dutch commonly-used phonetically-balanced narrative ‘Papa en Marloes’ (‘Papa and Marloes’ in English; Van de Weijer & Slijs et al., 1991): (1) ‘Papa en Marloes staan op het station.’ (in English ‘Papa and Marloes are at the station.’), (2) ‘Marloes kijkt naar links.’ (in English ‘Marloes looks to the left.’), (3) ‘In de verte ziet ze de trein al aankomen.’ (in English ‘In the distance she can see the train coming.’), and (4) ‘Het is al vijf over drie dus het duurt nog vier minuten.’ (in English ‘It is already five past three so it will take another four minutes.’).

The Word Experiment covered word lists that were selected from those in the three subsets A, B, and C constructed in the Dutch Intelligibility Assessment (DIA) task (De Bodt et al. 2006), which is also contained in the COPAS dataset. This DIA task was originally designed to assess intelligibility at the phoneme level, resulting in a measure called Phoneme Intelligibility (PhonI). The three subsets are constructed to assess initial consonants, final consonants, and medial vowels in CVC words, respectively. Note that different speakers received a variant of each subset, leading to different combinations of three word lists, whereas all speakers received the same four sentences in the Sentence Experiment.

2.2. Speakers

In total, 26 speakers with dysarthria and 10 healthy speakers were selected from the COPAS database, as described in a previous study (Xue et al., 2021b). These speakers covered different dysarthria types, severity levels of dysarthria, PhonI scores obtained through the original DIA task, age, and gender to ensure the diversity of speaker data. All of the speakers were involved in the Sentence Experiment, while only half of them were involved in the Word Experiment. Involving fewer speakers in the Word Experiment was to ensure that raters would be able to finish both experiments within one hour based on the fact that more words were contained in the word lists than in the sentences. Fig. 1 shows the distribution of the speakers over the four different levels (healthy, mild, moderate, and severe from low to high) of SevL. The number of healthy speakers is comparable to the numbers of speakers in the different levels of dysarthria. We included healthy speakers to allow comparisons with dysarthric speakers.

2.3. Expert raters

Raters for assessing speech intelligibility in both experiments were the same five Belgian Dutch-speaking speech-language pathologists (one male and four females) recruited from the University Antwerp Hospital. They all worked with individuals with communication disorders and were all familiar with evaluating and testing dysarthric individuals through the intelligibility tasks used in the two experiments.

2.4. Experimental procedure

In the listening experiments, all recordings covering both speech materials were made in a quiet clinical setting without a sound-attenuated booth, which was described in the COPAS manual, and had the same sound quality. Both listening experiments were conducted online through the survey tool Qualtrics on the same day, the Sentence Experiment first and the Word Experiment second,

Fig. 1. Distribution over four severity levels of dysarthria (SevL) of speakers in our two experiments.

with two resting hours in between. The raters gave their digital consent before they participated. All the instructions and explanations were presented in Belgian Dutch, the target language. Before the actual experiments, the raters familiarized themselves with the procedure of assessment through practice examples. Both experiments employed anchor items to ensure reliability. The recordings for these items were selected from healthy speakers and speakers with severe dysarthria from the COPAS dataset. They were presented at the beginning of the actual experiments and repeated after every ten utterances. The recordings used for the practice examples and anchor items were not from speakers involved in the two actual experiments. To avoid any systematic order effect on the assessment, the utterances (recordings) were randomized. Specifically, the utterances (recordings) were randomized in a way that every six consecutive samples were not from the same speakers and every two consecutive samples were not about the same sentences or subsets. The randomized order of samples was kept the same for all the raters.

In detail, the Sentence Experiment contained 144 utterances (recordings), consisting of the same set of four sentences read by 36 speakers. The Word Experiment involved 54 utterances, consisting of three word lists (three variants of three DIA subsets) read by 18 speakers. Each utterance was presented once to prevent the raters from adapting to speakers and speech materials. As described in Xue et al. (2021b), for each utterance, the raters received an orthographic transcription task (in AWTrans form) and a VAS task on the same page at the same time with AWTrans presented above VAS. The raters completed both tasks in the order they preferred. The AWTrans form of transcription allows not only existing words but also pseudo words. The VAS task was a horizontal scale ranging from 0 (not intelligible) to 100 (intelligible) with written instructions ‘Wat voor score zou u toekennen aan de spraakverstaanbaarheid?’ (in English ‘what score would you assign for speech intelligibility?’). The scale contained tick marks with numbers for every ten scores shown (e.g., 10, 20, 30, etc.) but no scale endpoints’ labels. Moreover, the raters in the Word experiment had to transcribe the whole words in the word lists without any phonemes being presented. This was different from the original DIA procedure, in which the listeners were asked to transcribe the missing target phonemes while the remaining phonemes of a word were presented.

2.5. Intelligibility measures

To obtain phoneme-level measures, we first cleaned the collected orthographic transcriptions by removing punctuation and symbols indicating missing words. Following this, we applied a Grapheme-to-Phoneme (G2P)² conversion for all the unique words in both the prompts and the orthographic transcriptions of all utterances. Then, we manually checked and corrected the transformed phonetic transcription of each word. Finally, we concatenated the phonetic transcriptions of words into phonetic transcriptions of sentences, word lists, and prompts.

Based on the phonetic transcriptions, two types of phoneme-level measures were computed: Accuracy of Phonemes (AcP) and Phonetic Distance (PhonD). The AcP was calculated as follows:

$$AcP = \frac{N_{match}}{N_{total}} \times 100, \quad (1)$$

where N_{total} denotes the total number of phonemes in the reference transcriptions and N_{match} denotes the number of matched phonemes between the reference and the phonetic transcriptions. The PhonD was calculated as follows:

$$PhonD = \begin{cases} \frac{Dist_{phoneme}}{N_{total}} \times 100, & \text{if } \frac{Dist_{phoneme}}{N_{total}} \leq 1 \\ 100, & \text{if } \frac{Dist_{phoneme}}{N_{total}} > 1 \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

where $Dist_{phoneme}$ denotes the sum of the phonetic distance between the reference and phonetic transcriptions calculated by ADAPT (Elffers et al., 2005), which is a dynamic programming algorithm that computes the optimal alignment between two strings of phonemes. The computed optimal alignment has the smallest phonetic distance between two strings of phonemes. For each pair of phonemes (one in reference and one in phonetic transcription), the phonetic distance is calculated as the total difference between the feature vectors of the pair of phonemes based on the feature-based distance metrics developed by Cucchiari (1993, 1996). These metrics present the feature vectors of all phonemes. In detail, as described and established by Cucchiari (1993, 1996), the feature vectors for vowels consist of five features (i.e., length, front/back, tongue, roundedness, and diphthong). The feature vectors for consonants consist of eleven features. These eleven features are place of articulation (plc), voice (voc), nasal (nas), stop (stp), glide (gld), lateral (lat), fricative (frc), trill (trl), aspirant (asp), dental (dnt), and strength (str). Table 1 presents an example of how the phonetic distance between two phonemes is calculated in ADAPT (Elffers et al., 2005).

2.6. Data analysis

All the following statistical analyses were conducted in RStudio (RStudio Team, 2020) with R version 4.0.2 (R Core Team, 2014). We first studied the descriptive results (mean and standard deviation) of the two types of phoneme-level intelligibility measures. For a detailed study of the AcP measure, we calculated AcP by phoneme categories. We distinguished three global AcP scores, namely for all phonemes (AcP_all), for consonants only (AcP_consonants), and for vowels only (AcP_vowels). We applied Levene’s test to study

² The applied G2P were conducted through the ‘‘Grapheme to Phoneme Converter’’ provided in <https://webservices.cls.ru.nl/g2pservice>.

Table 1

The feature vectors of phoneme /t/ and /s/ and the phonetic distance between them used in ADAPT (Elffers et al., 2005).

Feature vector	plc	voc	nas	stp	gld	lat	frc	trl	asp	dnt	str	Phonetic distance
/t/	4.0	1.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	
/s/	4.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	
Difference	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0

Note. plc: place of articulation; voc: voicing; nas: nasal; stp: stop; gld: glide; lat: lateral; frc: fricative; trl: trill; asp: aspirant; dnt: dental; str: strength.

whether the variances of the four measures between the two experiments are significant or not. We also applied Welch’s *t*-test to study whether the mean values are significant or not. We further studied whether the mean values of AcP between the two categories (i.e., consonants and vowels) are significant or not through paired *t*-test. The statistical analyses were implemented by using the *car* package (Fox, 2019).

To address the first research question regarding the reliability of AcP and PhonD, we applied Generalizability Theory to compute the D coefficient as interrater reliability by using the *gtheory* package (Moore, 2016). The reason for applying Generalizability Theory was that it can simultaneously deal with all sources of variance relevant in the same experiments (e.g., raters, speakers, and utterances). The model designs for the two experiments were different due to the speech materials. The model design for the Sentence Experiment was a fully-crossed design as *Rater* × *Sample* × *Speaker* because all four sentences (the same sample) from all 36 speakers were assessed by all five raters. The model design for the Word Experiment was a nested design as (*Sample:Speaker*) × *Rater* because word lists (different samples) were nested under speaker, the combination of which was assessed by the raters. More information and explanations about these model designs and their analyses can be found in Xue et al. (2021b).

To address the second research question regarding the validity of AcP and PhonD, we calculated Pearson correlations between our phoneme-level measures and three criterion measures, namely scores obtained from VAS, the accuracy of words (AcW) obtained from orthographic transcriptions in AWTrans form, and PhonI obtained from the original DIA task. The former two higher-level measures (i.e., VAS and AcW) and the phoneme-level measures investigated in this study were collected from the same two listening experiments. The PhonI obtained from the original DIA task was calculated as the percentage of correctly transcribed target phonemes over all three word lists. In more detail, these target phonemes were transcribed in the presence of the remaining phonemes of a word (e.g., transcribing target phoneme ‘n’ in ‘nit’ which was presented as ‘.it’). All three criterion measures were shown to be reliable and valid (Van Nuffelen et al., 2008; Xue et al., 2021b).

To address the third research question regarding the performance of measures in classifying speakers into two speaker types and four severity levels, we first aggregated the scores for speakers. For a detailed study of the AcP measure, we calculated AcP by phoneme categories. Aside from the three global AcP scores (i.e., AcP_all, AcP_consonants, and AcP_vowels), we computed detailed scores for place and manner of articulation for consonants and frontness and openness for vowels. The classes of consonants according to the place of articulation were labial (/p, b, f, v, m, ʋ/), alveolar (/t, d, s, z, n, l/), post-alveolar (/ʃ, ʒ/), dorsal (/k, g, x, ɣ, ŋ, j/), and glottal (/h/). The manner classes were plosive (/p, b, t, d, k, g/), fricative (/f, v, s, z, ʃ, ʒ, x, ɣ, h/), nasal (/m, n, ŋ/), trill (/r/), and approximant (/ʋ, l, j/). The frontness vowel classes were front (/ɪ, i, e, e:, ei/), central (/Y, y, ə, əy, ø:/), and back (/u, ʊ, o:, ɑ:, ɒ, ɔ:/). The openness classes were open (/ɑ, a:/), middle (/ɛ, e:, ə, o:, əy, ø:, ʌ, ei, ə/), and closed (/ɪ, i, Y, y, u/). In total, we calculated 20 phoneme-level intelligibility measures. The list of all intelligibility measures collected through the two experiments is shown in Table 2.

We visualized all 20 phoneme-level measures per speaker through boxplots over four SevL levels and calculated the Pearson correlations between those scores in the three sets of experiments. The three sets of experiments are the whole set of the Sentence Experiment (*N* = 36), a subset of the Sentence Experiment (*N* = 18) in which the same 18 speakers in the Word Experiment were involved, and the whole set of the Word Experiment (*N* = 18). We studied whether the variances and the mean values of all 20 phoneme-level measures between every two levels of severity are significant by applying Levene’s test and Welch’s *t*-test, respectively.

Finally, we used the scores of the different phoneme categories to conduct two classification tasks (i.e., speaker type and severity level) through Support Vector Machine (SVM) with Radial (Gaussian) kernel using 5-folds cross-validation. We applied three groups of

Table 2

The list of intelligibility measures collected through the two experiments.

Level of measures	Type of measures	Unit	Phoneme category	Names of measures	Number of measures
higher-level	VAS	utterance	–	VAS	2
	AcW	word	–	AcW	
phoneme-level	PhonD	phoneme	all phonemes	PhonD	20
	AcP	phoneme	all phonemes	AcP_all	
		consonant	all consonants	AcP_consonants	
			place of articulation	AcP_labial, AcP_alveolar, AcP_post-alveolar, AcP_dorsal, AcP_glottal	
			manner of articulation	AcP_plosive, AcP_fricative, AcP_nasal, AcP_trill,	
			approximant	AcP_approximant	
	vowel	all vowels	AcP_vowels		
	frontness of vowels	AcP_front, AcP_central, AcP_back			
	openness of vowels	AcP_open, AcP_middle, AcP_closed			

variables as predictors in SVM: (1) all 20 phoneme-level intelligibility measures, (2) two higher-level measures, and (3) combining these former groups, resulting in all 22 intelligibility measures. The higher-level measures were intended to explore whether these measures supplement or may be different from detailed phoneme-level measures. Moreover, our phoneme-level measures generally had very strong correlations (see Section 3.4). As this may impact the robustness of the SVM results, we also explored their classification power of these measures using Random Forest (RF). Furthermore, we applied a multinomial regression to study the relation between each of the 20 phoneme-level measures with SevL. Detailed information and the corresponding results about RF and the multinomial regression can be found in the Supplementary Materials.

The correlation results were interpreted based on the guidelines from Evans (1996, p. 146). That is, a correlation between 0.80 and 1.0 is ‘very strong’, between 0.60 and 0.79 is ‘strong’, between 0.40 and 0.59 is ‘moderate’, between 0.20 and 0.39 is ‘weak’, and even lower is ‘very weak’. The implementation of the analyses for the descriptive results and addressing the second and third research questions was conducted by using the *stats* (R Core Team, 2014), *caret* (Max, 2022), *e1071* (Meyer et al., 2021), and *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016) packages.

3. Results

3.1. General results of phoneme-level measures of intelligibility

The mean and standard deviation (SD) of the two types of phoneme-level intelligibility measures (i.e., PhonD and AcP) in both experiments are shown in Table 3. In particular, three global AcP scores were studied. In general, significantly higher mean AcP and lower mean PhonD values were found for the Sentence Experiment than for the Word Experiment (Welch’s *t*-test, $p < 0.001$). The variances between the two experiments were significantly different (Levene’s test, $p < 0.001$) for all four measures. Also, when comparing AcP between the two categories (i.e., consonants and vowels), the AcP of consonants showed significantly lower mean values than AcP of vowels in both experiments. The paired *t*-test reported $t(719) = -7.96$ ($p < 0.001$) for the Sentence Experiments and $t(269) = -2.6363$ ($p < 0.01$) for the Word Experiment.

3.2. Interrater reliability of phoneme-level measures of intelligibility

Table 4 shows the results of the interrater reliability (D coefficients) for PhonD and AcP of different categories in both experiments. In general, all four phoneme-level measures showed relatively high reliability values (> 0.90), except PhonD in the Sentence Experiment and AcP_vowels in the Word Experiment. Interestingly, even though both AcP and PhonD were extracted from the same phonetic transcriptions, AcP appeared to be more reliable than PhonD, especially in the Sentence Experiment. Surprisingly, the reliability for AcP of vowels in the Word Experiment was lower than all the other results. This may be due to the presence of pseudo words and the lack of contextual information.

3.3. Validity of phoneme-level measures of intelligibility

To investigate the validity of our phoneme-level measures, we correlated each with three criterion measures (i.e., VAS, AcW, and PhonI through the original DIA task) for both experiments. As shown in Table 5, both types of phoneme-level measures (i.e., AcP and PhonD) showed very strong correlations (magnitude > 0.90) with both VAS and AcW regardless of speech materials, whereas they showed weaker correlations (magnitude between 0.60 and 0.75) with PhonI.

3.4. Phoneme-level measures of intelligibility in classifying speakers

Fig. 2 illustrates the distributions of 20 phoneme-level measures for the four levels of SevL through boxplots in the whole set of the Sentence Experiment ($N = 36$), the subset of the Sentence Experiment ($N = 18$), and the Word Experiment ($N = 18$). In detail, these measures were PhonD, three global AcP scores for three different categories, namely one for all phonemes (AcP_all), one for only consonants (AcP_consonants), and one for only vowels (AcP_vowels), as well as AcP of the place and the manner of articulation for consonants and AcP of frontness and openness for vowels. We also applied *t*-test to explore whether the mean values of the 20 phoneme-level measures between every two levels of severity are significant or not. We summarized the significant results ($p < 0.05$) in Table 6.

Fig. 2 generally shows that in the whole set of the Sentence Experiment, the median of the AcP scores decreased and the median of

Table 3

Mean (Standard deviation) of the measures in the two experiments. Higher AcP scores are associated with higher intelligibility, while PhonD scores have the opposite direction.

Mean (Standard deviation)		Sentence experiment ($N = 36$)	Word experiment ($N = 18$)
PhonD	all phonemes	21.27 (31.53)	51.98 (30.83)
AcP	all phonemes (AcP_all)	90.01 (19.96)	71.38 (18.79)
	consonants (AcP_consonants)	89.08 (21.23)	70.51 (20.73)
	vowels (AcP_vowels)	91.90 (18.89)	73.01 (19.10)

Table 4

Interrater reliability (D coefficients) of our two types of phoneme-level measures (i.e., PhonD and AcP) for both experiments. AcP scores were calculated for all phonemes (AcP_all), for consonants only (AcP_consonants), and for vowels only (AcP_vowels).

Interrater reliability		Sentence experiment (N = 36)	Word experiment (N = 18)
PhonD	all phonemes	0.89	0.95
AcP	all phonemes (AcP_all)	0.93	0.97
	consonants (AcP_consonants)	0.93	0.97
	vowels (AcP_vowels)	0.90	0.83

Table 5

Correlations between criterion measures (VAS, AcW, and PhonI) and our phoneme-level measures (i.e., PhonD and AcP for all phonemes, consonants only and vowels only) for both experiments.

Correlations		Sentence experiment (N = 36)			Word experiment (N = 18)		
		VAS	AcW	PhonI	VAS	AcW	PhonI
PhonD	all phonemes	-0.96	-0.98	-0.65	-0.94	-0.98	-0.65
AcP	all phonemes (AcP_all)	0.97	0.95	0.67	0.97	0.95	0.74
	consonants (AcP_consonants)	0.97	0.96	0.68	0.97	0.93	0.72
	vowels (AcP_vowels)	0.96	0.93	0.63	0.90	0.95	0.74

Fig. 2. Boxplots of PhonD, accuracy of phonemes (AcP) in three categories, namely all phonemes (AcP_all), consonants only (AcP_consonants), and vowels only (AcP_vowels), AcP for place and manner of articulation for consonants and frontness and openness for vowels in the whole set of the Sentence Experiment (N = 36), the subset of the Sentence Experiment subset (N = 18), and the Word Experiment (N = 18) from top to bottom. The classes of consonants according to the place of articulation were labial (/p, b, f, v, m, θ/), alveolar (/t, d, s, z, n, l/), post-alveolar (/ʃ, ʒ/), dorsal (/k, g, x, γ, ŋ, j/), and glottal (/h/). The manner classes were plosive (/p, b, t, d, k, g/), fricative (/f, v, s, z, ʃ, ʒ, x, γ, h/), nasal (/m, n, ŋ/), trill (/r/), and approximant (/v, l, j/). The frontness vowel classes were front (/i, i, e, e:, ei/), central (/Y, y, ə, əy, ø:/), and back (/u, ɔ, o, a, a:, ʌu/). The openness classes were open (/a, a:/), middle (/e, e:, ə, o:, əy, ø:, ʌu, ei, ə/), and closed (/ɪ, i, Y, y, u/).

PhonD increased with increased severity levels of dysarthria. This tendency was further supported by the statistical results shown in Table 6. That is, significantly higher mean values of AcP and lower mean values of PhonD were frequently observed for lower severity levels of dysarthria. This tendency did not persist in the Word Experiment. In detail, although the median values for healthy speakers were consistently the highest and those for severe dysarthric speakers were the lowest, the median values for the middle two SevL levels were similar, but with sometimes one being higher than the other and sometimes the opposite. This was also supported by the statistical results that differences between mild and moderate levels were not significant for most of the 20 measures. Further, AcP_glottal showed different trends in the median values for the four SevL levels. We also did not observe any significant results in the

Table 6

The results of *t*-test for comparing the mean values of phoneme-level measures between every two levels of severity. Only significant results ($p < 0.05$) are reported.

<i>t</i> -test results	Sentence experiment ($N = 36$)						Sentence experiment ($N = 18$)						Word experiment ($N = 18$)					
	01	02	03	12	13	23	01	02	03	12	13	23	01	02	03	12	13	23
PhonD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
all	+	+	+	+	+	+	+						+	+	+			+
consonants	+	+	+	+	+	+							+	+	+			+
vowels	+	+	+	+	+	+		+					+		+			+
labial	+	+											+	+	+			+
alveolar		+	+	+	+	+							+	+	+			+
post-alveolar	+	+	+	+	+		+	+					+	+	+			+
dorsal	+	+	+	+	+								+		+			
glottal		+	+	+	+	+			+		+						-	
plosive	+	+	+	+	+	+							+	+	+			+
fricative		+	+	+	+	+							+		+			+
nasal	+	+	+	+	+										+			
trill	+	+	+	+	+			+	+				+	+	+			+
approximant	+	+	+		+	+							+	+	+			+
front		+	+	+	+	+		+		+			+		+			+
central		+		+											+			+
back	+	+	+		+			+					+	+	+	-		+
open	+	+	+		+	+		+					+		+			+
middle		+	+	+	+	+				+			+		+			+
closed		+	+	+	+		+						+		+			+

Note. Except PhonD, the others are all AcP scores; **01**: healthy vs mild; **02**: healthy vs moderate; **03**: healthy vs severe; **12**: mild vs moderate; **13**: mild vs severe; **23**: moderate vs severe; +: greater with $p < 0.05$; -: less with $p < 0.05$; an example: ‘02’ with ‘+’ means the mean values for healthy level are higher than those for moderate level.

mean values of AcP_glottal except between mild and severe levels. Moreover, the subset of the Sentence Experiment showed different results. Although the boxplots show decreases in the median values of AcP with increased severity levels, differences between most pairs of AcP scores were not statistically significant. In contrast, PhonD more frequently showed significant results.

Aside from the visualization of the phoneme-level measures, we further explored the correlations between them before applying any classification algorithms. The correlations between each pair of phoneme-level measures were generally very high in both sets of the Sentence Experiment (whole set: $Mean = 0.914$, $SD = 0.052$; subset: $Mean = 0.925$, $SD = 0.056$). This is in line with the boxplot results that all phoneme-level measures always showed similar trends. Differently, the correlations in the Word Experiment were slightly lower ($Mean = 0.724$, $SD = 0.243$) and those for AcP_glottal ($Mean = 0.112$, $SD = 0.95$) were very low. These results were also in line with trends represented in the boxplots. More detailed results about correlations can be found in Section S.1 in the Supplementary Materials.

Following the correlation calculation, we further explored the performance of our phoneme-level measures together with the two higher-level measures in three groups for classifying speakers into two types of speakers and four severity levels by using SVM. The results in Table 7 show higher accuracy values for the two-way speaker type classification than for the four-way severity level classification. This is the consequence of having more classes. In addition, the accuracy values in the Word Experiment were generally higher than those in the two sets of the Sentence Experiment. The differences between the Sentence Experiment and the Word Experiment could be due to the different characteristics of the two speech materials. Nevertheless, when combining all phoneme-level intelligibility measures, around half of the speakers were classified correctly in both classification tasks regardless of speech materials. Such results were also supported when using different algorithms such as multinomial regression and RF as shown in Figure S1 and Table S2 in the Supplementary Materials.

Furthermore, for speaker type classification, the accuracy values of the higher-level measures outperformed the phoneme-level

Table 7

Results for speaker type (healthy vs dysarthric) and severity level (healthy, mild, moderate, and severe) classification tasks using three groups of measures as independent variables in SVM implementation for the three sets of the experiments. Train = training speaker set; Valid = Validation speaker set.

Classification task	Independent variables (Input)	Sentence experiment ($N = 36$) Accuracy (Train/Valid)	Sentence experiment ($N = 18$) Accuracy (Train/Valid)	Word experiment ($N = 18$) Accuracy (Train/Valid)
speaker type	phoneme	0.88/0.83	0.96/0.80	1.00/0.90
	high	0.92/0.92	0.78/0.80	0.88/0.90
	all	0.88/0.84	0.99/0.85	1.00/0.90
severity level	phoneme	0.81/0.64	0.86/0.33	1.00/0.64
	high	0.59/0.56	0.64/0.55	0.58/0.54
	all	0.85/0.70	0.88/0.38	1.00/0.64

Note. “phoneme” – 20 phoneme-level intelligibility measures; “high” – 2 higher-level intelligibility measures; “all” – all 22 measures.

measures in the whole set of the Sentence Experiment, whereas in the other two sets, the phoneme-level measures outperformed the higher-level measures. For severity level classification, the phoneme-level measures outperformed the higher-level measures in all three sets.

Also, combining the higher-level measures (i.e., VAS and AcW) with the phoneme-level measures seems to increase the accuracy values to a limited extent. This might be because the higher-level measures were highly correlated with the phoneme-level measures, as shown in [Section 3.3](#), and consequently had a limited impact on the classification results when the number of predictors was large enough.

4. Discussion

In the present study, two types of phoneme-level measures were investigated (i.e., AcP and PhonD). AcP indicated whether a transcribed phoneme was correct or not, and PhonD showed how different a transcribed phoneme was from its reference phoneme. The phoneme-level measures were calculated based on the more permissive form of transcription (AWTrans), which allows all kinds of acceptable words, instead of the more common EWTrans, which allows only existing words. We considered two types of speech materials (i.e., meaningful sentences extracted from a narrative and word lists consisting of CVC existing and pseudo words). In particular, we studied these phoneme-level measures in terms of reliability, validity, and their performance in classifying speakers according to their speaker types and severity levels of dysarthria.

Our findings show that both types of measures showed largely similar reliability and validity in both speech materials, indicating that they can be used in future studies and clinical trials. Regarding their performance in classifying speakers, the type of speech material seems to be the most critical factor. That is, both types of measures can classify speakers into two speaker types and four severity levels of dysarthria to a certain extent when using meaningful sentences. In contrast, they are more successful in classifying speakers when using word lists.

Before answering the research questions, we will first discuss the general results of both types of measures in both speech materials. The result that AcP indicated higher intelligibility in the Sentence Experiment than in the Word Experiment may be explained in two ways. First, this is perhaps due to the contextual information involved in sentences compared to word lists. This seems to be in line with previous studies of word-level measures ([Hustad, 2007](#); [Miller, 2013](#); [Xue et al., 2021a, b](#); [Yorkston & Beukelman, 1978](#)) that higher scores were found for sentences than for word lists. Another possible explanation is the differences in raters' familiarity with the words. The raters were more familiar with the words involved in the sentences than those in the word lists, because these sentences were extracted from a narrative that was frequently used by them in clinical trials. Also, the words contained in the sentences were existing, commonly used words, whereas the words in the word lists contained pseudo words, which were more difficult to transcribe than existing words.

Furthermore, when comparing AcP scores between the two categories (i.e., consonants and vowels), we found significantly lower mean and higher standard deviations for the consonants than for the vowels, regardless of speech materials. This largely supports the finding by [Miyakoda \(2003\)](#) that consonants are more error-prone than vowels in both healthy and pathological speech.

4.1. RQ1: Interrater reliability of phoneme-level measures of intelligibility

Our first research question was to what extent these phoneme-level measures are reliable in the two types of speech materials. The generally very high reliability values (around 0.90) indicate that both types of phoneme-level measures are reliable regardless of speech materials. These findings are comparable to those in previous studies of phoneme-level measures. For instance, [De Bodt et al. \(2006\)](#) reported very high reliability values of PhonI, which was used to examine the validity of our phoneme-level measures, with an inter-rater reliability of 0.93 and intra-rater reliability of 0.91. Further, the relatively higher reliability values of AcP compared to PhonD seem to suggest that raters performed similarly in transcribing a phoneme correctly. In contrast, they probably transcribed different symbols for the same target phoneme, which resulted in different distance scores and, thus, caused slightly lower reliability values of PhonD.

Moreover, our AcP for both consonants and vowels categories performed surprisingly well in terms of reliability, unlike the results reported by [Van Haaften et al. \(2019\)](#). In fact, the authors did report high point-to-point interrater agreement (larger than 95%) for both consonants and vowels obtained from two raters for Dutch children speech of two tasks that were comparable to ours (i.e., picture naming and non-word imitation). However, they reported only sufficient reliability values of ICC for consonants and vowels. In detail, the reliability values for the percentage of consonants correct in syllable-initial position in both tasks were sufficient, with 0.80 in picture naming and 0.77 in non-word imitation. In contrast, the reliability values for the percentage of vowels correct were insufficient, with 0.59 in picture naming and 0.62 in non-word imitation. One possible explanation for the different results of reliability is the larger number of raters (5) in our current study compared to that (2) in [Van Haaften et al. \(2019\)](#).

4.2. RQ2: Validity of phoneme-level measures of intelligibility

Our second research question was to what extent these phoneme-level measures are valid in the two types of speech materials. We can conclude that both measures are valid to a large extent according to the very strong correlations (magnitude > 0.90) to two of the criterion measures (i.e., VAS and AcW) and the strong correlations (magnitude > 0.60) to PhonI regardless of speech materials.

The very strong correlations with VAS and AcW are easy to understand because VAS and the orthographic transcriptions for generating AcW, AcP, and PhonD were all collected in the same experiments. The very strong correlations with VAS seem to suggest

that the raters' global perception of intelligibility, as reflected by VAS, is highly correlated to articulation accuracy, as reflected by phoneme-level measures (AcP and PhonD). This substantially supports the previous findings of De Bodt et al. (2002) that articulation contributes the most to the overall intelligibility through a linear combination although these authors used rating scales for assessing articulation and the overall intelligibility.

In addition, unlike the very strong correlations of phoneme-level measures with VAS and AcW, both types of phoneme-level measures showed weaker correlations with PhonI. This may be because PhonI was obtained differently. PhonI was collected from a different speech material compared to the measures in the Sentence Experiment. For the Word Experiment, although PhonI and our two types of phoneme-level measures were collected from the same speech material, different procedures were used. In detail, PhonI was calculated as the percentage of correctly transcribed target phonemes with the rest phonemes of CVC words being presented (De Bodt et al., 2006; Middag et al., 2009), whereas our phoneme-level measures were collected without any phoneme being presented. In other words, our approach examined more phonemes and, thus, leads to more room for error and more information on articulation imprecision. Also, transcribing a target phoneme with the context of the rest phonemes of a word requires less effort than transcribing the whole word.

4.3. RQ3: Phoneme-level measures of intelligibility in classifying speakers to different speaker types and severity levels of dysarthria

Our third research question was how well these phoneme-level measures can classify speakers into different types and different severity levels of dysarthria. We can conclude that our phoneme-level measures were similarly distributed over severity levels of dysarthria within each type of speech material, but showed different trends in different speech materials. By combining all phoneme-level intelligibility measures, we were able to classify more than half of speakers correctly in both classification tasks regardless of speech materials, but the performance was much better when using word lists.

In general, the boxplots and the statistical results showed that intelligibility decreased for speakers with more severe dysarthria regardless of phoneme-level measures and speech materials. This seems to be in line with previous findings showing that higher-level measures of intelligibility were lower for speakers with more severe dysarthria (Hustad, 2007, 2008). However, meaningful sentences showed higher intelligibility than word lists, as reflected by the significantly higher mean AcP and lower mean PhonD values. This may be due to the contextual information in the sentences.

Furthermore, mixed trends were observed for different classes in the categories of consonants and vowels in different speech materials in terms of their median values and the sizes of boxes in the boxplots. For instance, moderate dysarthric speakers showed higher median and significantly higher mean values for the AcP of central vowels than mild dysarthric speakers in word lists, which was opposite to the results in meaningful sentences. Such mixed results in different speech materials, especially for dysarthric speakers, as well as the lower intelligibility in word lists compared to meaningful sentences, seem to broadly support the findings by Barreto and Ortiz (2010). They reported significant differences of a subword-level measure (i.e., percentage of correctly transcribed syllables) between sentences, lists of words, and lists of pseudowords for intelligible speakers and reported larger differences among less intelligible speakers. The authors inferred that these differences were due to the absence of semantic information in pseudowords, which led to increased sensitivity to acoustic-phonetic information, as reflected by the subword-level measure.

In addition, the AcP of the glottal consonant /h/ surprisingly showed lower median values for healthy speakers and mild dysarthric speakers than those for moderate and severe dysarthric speakers. We applied a linear regression analysis to explore whether age and utterance were significant predictors to the AcP of glottal consonant. The analysis was conducted on AcP scores averaged per speaker per utterance ($N = 36$). Note that having 36 samples instead of 54 samples was because we involved only two of the three word lists for the 18 speakers since the last one did not contain the glottal consonant. We observed that age and the interaction between age and utterance were significant ($p < 0.05$). We further checked the word lists and found that one possible reason is the specific combinations of vowels and consonants that follow it. That is, when /h/, as an initial consonant in our word lists, was followed by /un/, /ein/, /il/, /en/, /in/, which was the case mostly for healthy speakers and mild dysarthric speakers, it was often deleted or substituted. The vowels in these syllables were mainly front and closed vowels. However, when /h/ was followed by /an/, /an/, /yn/, /uf/, /o.n/, /o.s/, /op/, /lut/, /e/, which was the case mostly for moderate and severe dysarthric speakers, it was often perceived correctly. The vowels in these syllables were mainly back or front rounded vowels. We also checked the age of the speakers and found that some healthy speakers and mild dysarthric speakers were older than 60, while moderate and severe dysarthric speakers were always younger than 60 (Xue et al., 2021b). Since aging can affect the function of the larynx (Kent et al., 1999; Linville, 1996; Weismer & Liss, 1991) and consequently the production of glottal consonants, this could partly explain the results we obtained for the glottal consonant.

Moreover, we observed very strong correlations ($Mean > 0.90$) in the Sentence Experiment and relatively lower correlations ($Mean > 0.70$) in the Word Experiment. These results seem to suggest that our phoneme-level measures showed similar distributions of scores when using meaningful sentences. This also indicates that these measures refer to a similar construct of intelligibility. In contrast, we observed slightly lower correlations when using word lists. This suggests that our measures refer to slightly different constructs of intelligibility. Further, the very strong correlations prevented us from observing significant differences in measures between speakers of different severity levels. Such limits may be because our datasets were a mixture of speakers with different types of dysarthria and were limited in size. Thus, further research should focus on larger datasets with sufficient numbers of speakers with different types of dysarthria.

Regarding the two classification tasks, word lists generated better results than meaningful sentences according to the higher accuracy values. One possible explanation for the different performance in classifying speakers in the two types of speech materials is the difference in some characteristics of the speech materials. As we explained earlier in Section 4, these two materials differ in their semantic cues, contextual information, and word structures. These results also indicate that well-constructed word lists compared to

meaningful sentences are more useful and successful in collecting phoneme-level measures for classifying speakers either to different speaker types or severity levels. Also, the finding that speakers were classified differently depending on the type of speech material used suggests that different speech materials are needed to obtain a comprehensive picture of speakers' intelligibility at the phoneme level.

The higher-level measures showed similar results in different speech materials regardless of the classification task. These results seem to suggest that the higher-level intelligibility measures, which are also considered as global intelligibility scores, refer to similar constructs of intelligibility regardless of speech materials (sentences or words). In contrast, the phoneme-level measures showed better results in the Word Experiment than in both sets of the Sentence Experiment. These results suggest that the phoneme-level intelligibility measures refer to different constructs of intelligibility in different speech materials. This might be due to, again, the different characteristics of the speech materials, such as different statistics of phonemes and amounts of contextual information.

The difference between AcP and PhonD was minor in terms of correlations and their distributions. This suggests that both types of measures can be used in clinical trials. However, since PhonD contains information on how different a transcribed phoneme is from a reference, more research is necessary to refine and further elaborate potential, detailed differences between PhonD and AcP.

Overall, the results seem to suggest that our two types of phoneme-level measures can be used for both classification tasks to a great extent when using word lists and for classifying speaker types to a certain extent when using meaningful sentences. Further, it may be too soon to conclude whether our phoneme-level measures can be used for classifying severity levels when using meaningful sentences. In future studies, it would be necessary to collect measures on larger datasets with more speakers at different severity levels.

4.4. Limitations and future work

The present study has some limitations that should be considered. First, the results obtained in the present study for expert listeners might not generalize to naïve listeners who have no or limited experience in transcribing or are not trained for distinguishing sounds of minimal pairs of phonemes. In fact, differences between experienced and naïve listeners have been reported not only on intelligibility measures (Carvalho et al., 2020; Monsen, 1983) but also on listening efforts (Maruthy & Raj, 2014). Thus, future work can investigate the same measures through transcriptions collected from naïve raters and thus can compare the performance of measures between different types of raters. Second, the two types of speech materials employed in the present study differ not only in the presence of contextual information but also with regard to fine-grained characteristics, such as the word structures and the number of syllables per word. Although the selection of speech materials was limited because we used the existing dataset COPAS, the lack of control over such characteristics may lead to results that differ from those obtained from well-controlled speech materials. For instance, Odell et al. (1991) found more errors in polysyllabic than monosyllabic words with both types of words being examined in isolation. However, it is difficult to draw the same conclusion from the current study. This is because words in the sentences consisted of polysyllabic and monosyllabic words, which is actually what happens in real life, whereas only monosyllabic words were contained in the word lists since these words were designed to assess target phonemes in CVC lexical structure. Therefore, more research is necessary to refine and further elaborate our novel findings.

4.5. Strengths

Our findings raise several important points for discussion. First, we contribute to the research on phoneme-level measures by examining the reliability and validity of two types of phoneme-level measures in two types of speech materials. The high reliability and validity of the two types of phoneme-level measures support their usage in clinical practice and research. Moreover, word lists perform better than meaningful sentences in classifying speakers in the two tasks. These findings indicate that speakers may articulate differently when receiving different levels of linguistic cues in speech materials. Therefore, as previous studies have suggested (Hustad, 2007; Yorkston & Beukelman, 1978), different speech materials should be considered when evaluating speech intelligibility, not only for word- and sentence-level measures but also for phoneme-level measures.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, this study comprehensively analyzed two types of phoneme-level measures collected from experienced, well-trained expert raters for two types of speech materials. Both types of phoneme-level measures are comparably reliable and valid. They show acceptable results in classifying speakers into two speaker types and four severity levels of dysarthria regardless of speech materials. Word lists show slightly higher levels of accuracy for both classification tasks compared to meaningful sentences. This is largely caused by different word structures, degrees of contextual information, and statistics of phonemes in the two speech materials, as well as individual differences. In turn, the different results in the two speech materials suggest that different speech materials are needed to evaluate speakers' intelligibility at phoneme level. Our findings show an advantage for using word lists in clinical practice and research. On the other hand, meaningful sentences can be used as an alternative to word lists a) to distinguish speakers and b) to evaluate articulation problems, which can help diagnosis to a certain extent. To further refine our findings, future studies may focus on well-constructed sentences or sentences with phoneme and word structures comparable to those in word lists.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Wei Xue: Methodology, Software, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Roeland van Hout:** Formal

analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Catia Cucchiari**: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Helmer Strik**: Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

We report no potential conflict of interest.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant number 766287.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.jcomdis.2023.106301](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcomdis.2023.106301).

References

- Abur, D., Enos, N. M., & Stepp, C. E. (2019). Visual analog scale ratings and orthographic transcription measures of sentence intelligibility in Parkinson's disease with variable listener exposure. *American Journal of Speech-Language Pathology*, 28(3), 1222–1232.
- Ansel, B. M., & Kent, R. D. (1992). Acoustic-phonetic contrasts and intelligibility in the dysarthria associated with mixed cerebral palsy. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 35(2), 296–308.
- Barreto, S. D. S., & Ortiz, K. Z. (2010). Intelligibility: Effects of transcription analysis and speech stimulus. *Pró-Fono Revista de Atualização Científica*, 22, 125–130.
- Barreto, S. dos S., & Ortiz, K. (2008). Intelligibility measurements in speech disorders: A critical review of the literature. *Pró-Fono Revista de Atualização Científica*, 20(3), 201–206.
- Barreto, S. dos S., & Ortiz, K. (2016). Protocol for the evaluation of speech intelligibility in dysarthrias: Evidence of reliability and validity. *Folia Phoniatrica et Logopaedica*, 67(4), 212–218.
- Cannito, M. P., Suiter, D. M., Beverly, D., Chorna, L., Wolf, T., & Pfeiffer, R. M. (2012). Sentence intelligibility before and after voice treatment in speakers with idiopathic Parkinson's disease. *Journal of Voice*, 26(2), 214–219.
- Carvalho, J., Cardoso, R., Guimarães, I., & Ferreira, J. J. (2020). Speech intelligibility of Parkinson's disease patients evaluated by different groups of healthcare professionals and naïve listeners. *Logopedics Phoniatrics Vocology*, 1–7.
- Cucchiari, C. (1993). *Phonetic transcription: A methodological and empirical study*. University of Nijmegen, the Netherlands. Ph.D. dissertation.
- Cucchiari, C. (1996). Assessing transcription agreement: Methodological aspects. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, 10/2, 131–155. <https://doi.org/10.3109/02699209608985167>
- De Bodt, M., Güns, C., & Van Nuffelen, G. (2006). *NSVO: Nederlandstalig spraakverstaanbaarheidsonderzoek*. Herentals: Vlaamse Vereniging voor Logopedisten.
- De Bodt, M. S., Huici, M. E. H. D., & Van De Heyning, P. H. (2002). Intelligibility as a linear combination of dimensions in dysarthric speech. *Journal of Communication Disorders*, 35(3), 283–292.
- Dongilli, P. (1994). Semantic context and speech intelligibility. In J. Till, K. Yorkston, & D. Beukelman (Eds.), *Motor speech disorders: Advances in assessment and treatment* (pp. 175–191). Baltimore, MD: Paul H. Brookes.
- Elffers, B., Van Bael, C., & Strik, H. (2005). *Algorithm for dynamic alignment of phonetic transcriptions*. The Netherlands: Department of Language and Speech. Radboud University Nijmegen. Technical Report.
- Evans, J. D. (1996). *Straightforward statistics for the behavioral sciences*. Pacific Grove, CA: Brooks/Cole Publishing.
- Fox, J., & Weisberg, S. (2019). *An R companion to applied regression* (3rd edition). Thousand Oaks CA: Sage. <https://socialsciences.mcmaster.ca/jfox/Books/Companion/>.
- Furia, C. L., Kowalski, L. P., Latorre, M. R., Angelis, E. C., Martins, N. M., Barros, A. P., & Ribeiro, K. C. (2001). Speech intelligibility after glossectomy and speech rehabilitation. *Archives of Otolaryngology-Head & Neck Surgery*, 127(7), 877–883.
- Ganzeboom, M., Bakker, M., Cucchiari, C., & Strik, H. (2016). Intelligibility of disordered speech: Global and detailed scores. *Proceedings of Interspeech*, 2503–2507.
- Hodge, M. M., & Gotzke, C. L. (2014). Construct-related validity of the TOCS measures: Comparison of intelligibility and speaking rate scores in children with and without speech disorders. *Journal of Communication Disorders*, 51, 51–63.
- Hustad, K. C. (2006). Estimating the intelligibility of speakers with dysarthria. *Folia Phoniatrica et Logopaedica*, 58(3), 217–228.
- Hustad, K. C. (2007). Effects of speech stimuli and dysarthria severity on intelligibility scores and listener confidence ratings for speakers with cerebral palsy. *Folia Phoniatrica et Logopaedica*, 59(6), 306–317.
- Hustad, K. C. (2008). The relationship between listener comprehension and intelligibility scores for speakers with dysarthria. *Journal of Speech Language and Hearing Research*, 51(3), 562–573.
- Ishikawa, K., Webster, J., & Ketring, C. (2020). Agreement between transcription- and rating-based intelligibility measurements for evaluation of dysphonic speech in noise. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, 1–13.
- Katz, L., & Frost, R. (1992). Reading in different orthographies: The orthographic depth hypothesis. In R. Frost, & L. Katz (Eds.), *Orthography, phonology, morphology, and meaning* (pp. 67–84). Amsterdam: New Holland.
- Kent, R. D., Weismer, G., Kent, J. F., & Rosenbek, J. C. (1989). Toward phonetic intelligibility testing in dysarthria. *Journal of Speech and Hearing Disorders*, 54(4), 482–499.
- Kent, R. D., Weismer, G., Kent, J. F., Vorperian, H. K., & Duffy, J. R. (1999). Acoustic studies of dysarthric speech: Methods, progress, and potential. *Journal of Communication Disorders*, 32(3), 141–186.
- Kim, H., Hasegawa-Johnson, M., & Perlman, A. (2011). Vowel contrast and speech intelligibility in dysarthria. *Folia Phoniatrica et Logopaedica*, 63(4), 187–194.
- Landerl, K., & Reitsma, P. (2005). Phonological and morphological consistency in the acquisition of vowel duration spelling in Dutch and German. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 92(4), 322–344.
- Levy, E. S., Leone, D., Moya-Gale, G., Hsu, S. C., Chen, W., & Ramig, L. O. (2016). Vowel intelligibility in children with and without dysarthria: An exploratory study. *Communication Disorders Quarterly*, 37(3), 171–179.
- Levy, E. S., Moya-Galé, G., Chang, Y. H. M., Freeman, K., Forrest, K., Brin, M. F., & Ramig, L. A. (2020). The effects of intensive speech treatment on intelligibility in Parkinson's disease: A randomised controlled trial. *EclinicalMedicine*, 24, Article 100429.
- Linville, S. E. (1996). The sound of senescence. *Journal of Voice*, 10, 190–200.

- Liss, J. M., Spitzer, S. M., Caviness, J. N., & Adler, C. (2002). The effects of familiarization on intelligibility and lexical segmentation in hypokinetic and ataxic dysarthria. *Journal of Acoustical Society of America*, 112(6), 10.
- Maruthy, S., & Raj, N. (2014). Relationship between speech intelligibility and listener effort in Malayalam-speaking individuals with hypokinetic dysarthria. *Journal of Speech, Language and Hearing*, 17(4), 237–245.
- Max, M. (2022). caret: Classification and regression training. R package version 6.0-91. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=caret>.
- Meyer, D., Dimitriadou, E., Hornik, K., Weingessel, A. and Leisch F. (2021). e1071: Misc functions of the department of statistics, probability theory group (Formerly: E1071), TU Wien. R package version 1.7-6. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=e1071>.
- Middag, C. (2012). *Automatic analysis of pathological speech*. Ghent, Belgium: Ghent University, Department of Electronics and information systems.
- Middag, C., Martens, J.P., Van Nuffelen, G., & De Bodt, M. (2009). DIA: A tool for objective intelligibility assessment of pathological speech. In *6th international workshop on models and analysis of vocal emissions for biomedical applications*, 165–167.
- Miller, N. (2013). Measuring up to speech intelligibility. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*, 48(6), 601–612.
- Miller, N., & Bloch, S. (2017). A survey of speech–Language therapy provision for people with post-stroke dysarthria in the UK. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*, 52(6), 800–815.
- Miyakoda, H. (2003). Speech errors in normal and pathological speech: Evidence from Japanese. *Journal of Multilingual Communication Disorders*, 1(3), 210–221.
- Monsen, R. (1983). The oral speech intelligibility of hearing-impaired talkers. *Journal of Speech and Hearing Disorders*, 48, 286–296.
- Moore, C.T. (2016). gtheory: Apply generalizability theory with R. [Computer software]. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=gtheory>.
- Nakayama, K., Yamamoto, T., Oda, C., Sato, M., Murakami, T., & Horiguchi, S. (2020). Effectiveness of Lee Silverman voice treatment® LOUD on Japanese-speaking patients with Parkinson's disease. *Rehabilitation Research and Practice*.
- Odell, K., McNeil, M. R., Rosenbek, J. C., & Hunter, L. (1991). Perceptual characteristics of vowel and prosody production in apraxic, aphasic, and dysarthric speakers. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 34(1), 67–80.
- Platt, L. J., Andrews, G., & Howie, P. M. (1980). Dysarthria of adult cerebral palsy: II. Phonemic analysis of articulation errors. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 23(1), 41–55.
- R Core Team (2014). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. [Computer software]. <http://www.R-project.org/>.
- RStudio Team (2020). RStudio: Integrated development for R. [Computer software]. <http://www.rstudio.com/>.
- Stipanovic, K. L., Tjaden, K., & Wilding, G. (2016). Comparison of intelligibility measures for adults with Parkinson's disease, adults with multiple sclerosis, and healthy controls. *Journal of Speech Language and Hearing Research*, 59(2), 230.
- Sussman, J. E., & Tjaden, K. (2012). Perceptual measures of speech from individuals with Parkinson's disease and multiple sclerosis: Intelligibility and beyond. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 55, 1208–1219.
- Tjaden, K. (2007). Segmental articulation in motor speech disorders. In G. Weismer (Ed.), *Motor speech disorders: Essays for ray Kent* (pp. 151–186). Plural Publishing.
- Tjaden, K., Kain, A., & Lam, J. (2014). Hybridizing conversational and clear speech to investigate the source of increased intelligibility in speakers with Parkinson's disease. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 57(4), 1191–1205.
- Tjaden, K., & Liss, J. M. (1995b). The influence of familiarity on judgments of treated speech. *American Journal of Speech-Language Pathology*, 4(1), 39–48.
- Tjaden, K., & Wilding, G. (2010). Effects of speaking task on intelligibility in Parkinson's disease. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, 25, 155–168.
- Tjaden, K. K., & Liss, J. M. (1995a). The role of listener familiarity in the perception of dysarthric speech. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, 9(2), 139–154.
- Van de Weijer, J., & Slis, I. (1991). Nasaliteitsmeting met de nasometer. *Logopedie en Foniatrie*, 63, 97–101.
- Van Haften, L., Diepeveen, S., van den Engel-Hoek, L., Jonker, M., de Swart, B., & Maassen, B. (2019). The psychometric evaluation of a speech production test battery for children: The reliability and validity of the computer articulation instrument. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 62(7), 2141–2170.
- Van Nuffelen, G., De Bodt, M., Guns, C., Wuyts, F., & Van de Heyning, P. (2008). Reliability and clinical relevance of segmental analysis based on intelligibility assessment. *Folia Phoniatrica et Logopaedica*, 5.
- Van Riper, C., & Emerick, L. L. (1984). *Speech correction: An introduction to speech pathology and audiology*. Prentice Hall.
- Weismer, G., & Liss, J. M. (1991). Age and speech motor control. In D. Ripich (Ed.), *Handbook of aging and communication* (pp. 205–226). Austin, TX: PRO-ED.
- Wickham, H. (2016). ggplot2: Elegant graphics for data analysis. [Computer software]. <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>.
- Xue, W., van Hout, R., Cucchiari, C., & Strik, H. (2021b). Assessing speech intelligibility of pathological speech: test types, ratings and transcription measures. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*. Advance online publication. DOI: 10.1080/02699206.2021.2009918.
- Xue, W., van Hout, R., Boogmans, F., Ganzeboom, M., Cucchiari, C., & Strik, H. (2021a). Speech intelligibility of dysarthric speech: Human scores and acoustic-phonetic features. *Proc. Interspeech*, 2911–2915.
- Yorkston, K. M., & Beukelman, D. R. (1978). A comparison of techniques for measuring intelligibility of dysarthric speech. *Journal of Communication Disorders*, 11(6), 499–512.
- Yorkston, K. M., & Beukelman, D. R. (1980). A clinician-judged technique for quantifying dysarthric speech based on single-word intelligibility. *Journal of Communication Disorders*, 13(1), 15–31.
- Yorkston, K. M., & Beukelman, D. R. (1981). Communication efficiency of dysarthric speakers as measured by sentence intelligibility and speaking rate. *Journal of Speech and Hearing Disorders*, 46(3), 296–301.
- Yuan, F., Guo, X., Wei, X., Xie, F., Zheng, J., Huang, Y., ... Wang, Q. (2020). Lee Silverman voice treatment for dysarthria in patients with Parkinson's disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *European Journal of Neurology*, 27(10), 1957–1970.